

APPLICATION FORM (full project proposal)

2021 Interdisciplinarity call for projects

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Application form

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Deadline for submission of complete proposals:

28 FEBRUARY 2022, 12-noon (Paris)

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1. General information

1.1 Project identification

Project title	What Neuroscience in the Anthropocene era?	
Project acronym	UNITÆ	
Keywords (maximum 10)	innovative practice, collective change, social behaviour, climate anxiety, computing, sustainable development, lab waste	
Planned schedule for the project (start and end)	01/10/2022	30/09/2025
Duration of the project (in months)	36	

1.2 Scientific and technical leader for the project (STL) and internal structure with which they are affiliated

Surname	<u>Schön</u>
First name	<u>Daniele</u>
Role (e.g.: MCF, PR, CD, DR, etc.)	<u>DR</u>
Contact details (E-mail + Tel)	<u>daniele.schon@univ-amu.fr, 0491423100</u>
Research unit (Name + Acronym) <i>Unit with which the STL is affiliated</i>	<u>Institut de Neurosciences des Systèmes, INS</u>
Research team (Name + Acronym) <i>Team within the unit of which the candidate is a member</i>	<u>Dynamiques des Processus Cognitifs, DCP</u>
Learning and teaching department (Name + Acronym) <i>Only for personnel affiliated with a learning and teaching department within the University</i>	

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<i>If affiliated with Ecole Central or Science Po Aix: also add this information here</i>	
Employed by (e.g.: AMU, CNRS, AP-HM, etc.)	CNRS

1.3 Partner(s) in implementation

Add as many partners as necessary

Partner 1 co-PI	
Type of partner (1 answer only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Aix-Marseille site research unit ² <input type="checkbox"/> AMU learning and teaching department or school on the Aix-Marseille ² site (Science Po Aix, Centrale Marseille) <input type="checkbox"/> Aix-Marseille-affiliated institute <input type="checkbox"/> Other internal structure (Doctoral schools, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Organisation outside the Aix-Marseille ² site
Name (full + Project acronym)	Institut de Neurosciences de la Timone, INT
Field of specialisation	Computer science
Contact person for the project (Full name, Contact e-mail + tel)	Julien Lefevre, julien.lefevre@univ-amu.fr

Because of the very large number of partners of this project we decided to include a summary table rather than duplicating the proposed form for every partner. All requested information are available in the summary table.

² The Aix-Marseille site - within A*Midex - includes AMU and the 7 IDEX partners: CNRS, INSERM, CEA, IRD, Centrale Marseille, Sciences Po Aix, and AP-HM

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Summary table of all partners. Laboratory representatives are in **bold**. All partners are AMU UMR.

[1] CRMBM : Center for Magnetic Resonance in Biology and Medicine, [2] IBDM : Institut de Biologie du Développement de Marseille, [3] INMED : Institut de Neurobiologie de la Méditerranée, [4] INP : Institut de Neurophysiopathologie, [5] INS : Institut de Neurosciences des Systèmes, [6] INT : Institut de Neurosciences de la Timone, [7] LNC : Laboratoire de Neurosciences Cognitives, [8] LPC : Laboratoire de Psychologie Cognitive, [9] LPS : Laboratoire de Psychologie Sociale, [10] UNIS : Unité des canaux Ioniques et de la Synapse, [11] Institut Fresnel

Researchers involved	UMR	Main discipline	mail
Callot Virginie	CRMBM	Imaging and Eng.	virginie.callot@univ-amu.fr
Costes Claire	CRMBM	Imaging and Eng.	claire.costes@univ-amu.fr
Girard Olivier	CRMBM	Imaging and Eng.	olivier.girard@univ-amu.fr
Sourdon Joevin	CRMBM	Imaging and Eng.	joevin.sourdon@univ-amu.fr
Le Troter Arnaud	CRMBM	Computer science	arnaud.le-troter@univ-amu.fr
Zaaraoui Wafaa	CRMBM	Imaging and Eng.	wafaa.zaaraoui@univ-amu.fr
Chaigne Thomas	Fresnel (Mosaic)	Imaging and Eng.	thomas.chaigne@univ-amu.fr
Beclin Christophe	IBDM	Neuroscience	christophe.beclin@univ-amu.fr
Francis Castets	IBDM	Neuroscience	francis.castets@univ-amu.fr
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Feron François	INP	Neuroscience	francois.feron@univ-amu.fr
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Besson Mireille	LNC	Cognitive neuro	mireille.besson@univ-amu.fr
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Longcamp Marieke	LNC	Cognitive neuro	marieke.longcamp@univ-amu.fr
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Strube Caroline	LNC	Ethics	caroline.strube@univ-amu.fr
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Anton Jean-Luc	INT : Centre IRM	Imaging and Eng.	jean-luc.anton@univ-amu.fr
Badier Jean-Michel	INS : Centre MEG	Imaging and Eng.	jean-michel.badier@univ-amu.fr
Bénar Christian	INS : Centre MEG	Imaging and Eng.	christian.benar@univ-amu.fr
Bertoldo Raquel	LPS	Social psychology	raquel.bohn-bertoldo@univ-amu.fr
Marcaggi Païkan	UNIS	Neuroscience	paikan.marcaggi@univ-amu.fr

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1.4 Disciplines and interdisciplinarity

Disciplinary field(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Human and Social Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Sciences <input type="checkbox"/> Physics <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Computing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental science <input type="checkbox"/> Chemistry <input type="checkbox"/> Planet and Universe <input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cognitive sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Economics and quantitative finance <input type="checkbox"/> Non-linear science
Discipline(s)	<p>Depending on the discipline(s) indicated above, select the sub-discipline(s) from the list published at: HAL</p> <p><u>Neurosciences, psychologie, AI, traitement du signal, informatique, apprentissage, linguistique</u></p>
Indicate the name and acronym for the Aix-Marseille-affiliated institute to which you belong	<p>CRMBM : Center for Magnetic Resonance in Biology and Medicine, Fresnel : Institut Fresnel, IBDM: Institut de Biologie du Développement de Marseille, INMED : Institut de Neurobiologie de la Méditerranée, INP : Institut de Neurophysiopathologie, INS : Institut de Neurosciences des Systèmes, INT : Institut de Neurosciences de la Timone, LNC : Laboratoire de Neurosciences Cognitives, LPC : Laboratoire de Psychologie Cognitive, LPS : Laboratoire de Psychologie Sociale, UNIS : Unité des canaux Ioniques et de la Synapse Imaging Platforms: Centre IRM-INT@CERIMED, Centre MEG, CRMBM</p>
AMU interdisciplinary research direction (<u>1 answer only</u>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Humanities <input type="checkbox"/> Energy <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> Science & Advanced Technology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Health & Life Sciences

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1.5 Budget

Overall budget for the project (€) (A + B)	110052€
Assistance requested from A*Midex (€) (A)	100000€
Other income and funding (€) (B)	10052€

1.6 Confidentiality

Specific confidentiality requirement?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
If yes, reason and details of requirements	

2. Abstract

This (non-confidential) abstract may be communicated in the context of the selection process when seeking experts (Recommendation: max. 1500 characters including spaces)

It is recommended that you take particular care when presenting the objective of the project in order to:

- *Encourage the acceptance of role of expert by the people contacted so as to allow your proposal to be appropriately assessed.*
- *(If the project is retained) be able to publish it for communication and mediation ends, for reading by audiences outside the project's disciplinary field. The text must therefore be as clear as possible, indicating the societal and/or technical challenges targeted.*

French version

Depuis peu, nous assistons à une augmentation spectaculaire des initiatives de la communauté scientifique pour mettre en garde contre les catastrophes environnementales. Les neurosciences peuvent contribuer activement à une meilleure compréhension à la fois des processus qui ont conduit notre société à devenir ce qu'elle est, et des processus psychologiques et neurophysiologiques permettant un changement des habitudes. En outre, les neuroscientifiques doivent examiner attentivement si et comment s'adapter à la crise climatique, en termes de sujets de recherche, de pratiques de recherche et de programmes d'enseignement.

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Le projet vise à :

- définir les questions neuroscientifiques pertinentes pour comprendre la crise climatique actuelle et suggérer de nouvelles orientations
- structurer une série de réunions interdisciplinaires afin de préciser le rôle des neurosciences à l'ère de l'Anthropocène
- intégrer une vision sociologique et engager une discussion sur l'avenir de la communauté des neurosciences face à la crise climatique
- améliorer les pratiques de recherche en neurosciences en matière d'environnement

9 laboratoires sur les 9 de la communauté NeuroMarseille sont représentés dans le projet actuel, avec une grande diversité de disciplines et de profils professionnels.

Ce projet permettra 1) de favoriser un effort de structuration sur une thématique innovante et pertinente 2) d'amorcer une transformation des pratiques scientifiques et de l'enseignement, respectueuse des enjeux environnementaux et socio-économiques 3) d'accroître la dynamique de l'Institut NeuroMarseille en termes d'axes de recherche innovants et transdisciplinaires.

English version

Recently, we have seen a dramatic increase of initiatives from the scientific community aimed to warn of the environmental disasters. Neuroscience can actively contribute to a better understanding of both the processes that led our society to become the way it is, and the psychological and neurophysiological processes allowing a change in habits. Moreover, neuroscientists need to carefully consider whether and how to adapt to the climate crisis, in terms of research topics, research practices and educational curricula.

The project aims at:

- redefining neuroscientific questions that may be relevant for understanding the actual crisis as well as suggesting new directions
- structuring a series of interdisciplinary meetings bringing their perspective on neuroscience at the era of Anthropocene
- adopting a collective vision and engaging in a discussion about the future of the community with respect to the climate crisis
- improving scientific practices in respect of environmental issues

9 Laboratories out of 9 of the NeuroMarseille community are represented in the current project, with a great diversity of disciplines and professional profiles.

This project will 1) foster a structuring effort on an innovative and relevant topic 2) ignite a transformation of scientific practices and education, respectful of both environmental and socio-economic challenges 3) increase the dynamics of the NeuroMarseille Institute in terms of innovative and transdisciplinary research lines.

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3. Quality and ambitions of the project

3.1. Context

Briefly present the general context and the challenges to which the project relates, in scientific terms. Present how the project contributes to the dynamics of the institute in terms of returns for the site (impact in scientific, pedagogical, international and innovation terms).

The state of the earth is undeniably deteriorating. Sharing the facts about the impact of human activities and developing responses that meet the challenges of maintaining the planet livable is becoming more urgent from day to day. To meet these challenges, the university, as the main actor in producing and sharing scientific knowledge, can play a decisive role: documenting the transformations of the planet and its impact on human beings, contributing to forging bold solutions and training students, the citizens who will shape the societies of tomorrow.

In the last years, we have seen a dramatic increase of initiatives from the scientific community to warn of the environmental disasters, among many others an article signed by 15.000 scientists [1] or tribunes coming from higher education stakeholders [2] or directly from students [3]. Those initiatives have percolated into concrete entities (e.g in France labos1point5 a group (GDR) to decarbonize research [4] or Atecopol [5], a pluri-disciplinary academic collective interested in thinking the diverse implications of ecological changes). The systemic nature of the environmental crisis calls for transdisciplinary approaches but scientific communities have also a crucial role to play 1) in embodying exemplarity 2) promoting research directions compatible with the "planetary boundaries" (in the sense of [6]). This introspective/reflexive approach of scientists on their own practices is more and more documented with very concrete guidelines to make research more sustainable [7].

Among other scientific fields, the neuroscience community has recently realized the research impacts, in terms of greenhouse gas emissions (equipments and computing, cf [8]) and also waste [9] with emerging solutions ([10], see also the OHBM special interest group [11]) and possible thematic redirections toward neuroscience for climate [12]. Indeed, one of the object of neuroscience being to understand the neural bases of behaviour, the field may play **a role in understanding the processes that go from awareness to changes in daily habits**. Engaging neuroscience in such a process requires to be cautious. First, buzz in the media and the scientific controversies about popularizing books (e.g. « Le bug humain » by Sébastien Bohler) renew the need of scientific rigor. Second, it is also clear that both individual actions, that can be better understood by psychological and neuroscientific research, and social, societal and political dimensions have to be taken into account in future decisions made to reduce the environmental footprint.

In such a collective perspective, two aspects seem particularly relevant for neuroscience: 1) the climate crisis creates instability: more and more students and researchers are questioning the meaning of their studies/research at the era of Anthropocene. It is not only a phenomenon documented in media

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but also by reports commissioned by academic institutes such as INRIA (« report » MakeSEnS [13]) or at the core of new academic tracks such as masters in ecological redirections (for example [14]). **A prospective approach regarding the future organisation of the neuroscientific field seems unavoidable on the long term.** 2) there is an increasing tension between main stream thinking of scientific progress on the one side, that may be seen as an amplification of environmental crisis and, on the other side, the emergence of slow science approaches [15] that are gaining popularity in hard sciences and neuroscience [16, 17] without denying scientific progress.

In a nutshell, neuroscience can **actively contribute to a better understanding** of the cognitive and social processes that contributed to change our society to become the way it is and of the processes needed for the engagement allowing a change in habits. Moreover, neuroscience needs to **carefully consider how to adapt** to the climate crisis, in terms of **research topics, research practices, educational curricula and interactions with the non academic world**. As a fundamentally multi-disciplinary field involving a large diversity of technologies, neuroscience represents an exceptional domain to assess the ecological footprints of ongoing research projects and rethink them in terms of their societal relevance.

For these various reasons this project will certainly contribute to **increase and widen the dynamics of the NeuroMarseille Institute**, in terms of scientific advances, pedagogical development and, most importantly, innovative research lines and practices. More precisely, in terms of scientific outcome, this project will promote research that will help to better understand the complex human behaviour facing the environmental challenges (see below WP1) and related cognitive and neurophysiological processes. Second, in terms of pedagogical development, this research will be carried on during Master internships and will be coordinated with the Neuroscience curricula. Moreover, several seminars and workshops will be organised and they will be accessible to students (WP2). These seminars may, in due time, turn into regular classes in the Neuroscience and Cognitive Science curricula. Finally, as far as we know, this is the first project gathering a large neuroscience community on environmental issues : **all laboratories of NeuroMarseille are partners of this project !** As such our project may promote the AMU Neuroscience Institute at the National and International levels on a topic that is going to receive more and more attention in the years to come.

3.2. Concept and aims of the project

Present the overall objectives of the project, describe any novel aspects with respect to the topic addressed.

The aims of the current project are to gather a rather large number of scientists from each of the AMU neuroscience laboratories (NeuroMarseille) to **commit to an environmentally responsible research**. More precisely, this can be declined in several different but inter-related aims:

- defining **neuroscientific questions** that may be relevant for understanding the actual crisis as well as suggesting new directions and solutions. These questions will be addressed *via* an ensemble of interconnected internships (see WP1).
- structuring a series of regular **interdisciplinary meetings** bringing their perspective on neuroscience at the era of anthropocene or more largely on the relations between science, society and environment (WP2).

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- consider the **NeuroMarseille community as an object of study** adopting a sociological and philosophical vision and engaging in a discussion about shared values, unthought and wills for the future of the community with respect to the climate crisis (WP2).
- identifying, sharing and promoting the existing virtuous practices and engaging in a scientific evaluation of the major impact of neuroscientific research. **Improving scientific practices** in respect of environmental issues (WP3).

Importantly, 2022 has been proclaimed by the UNESCO the International Year of Basic Sciences for Sustainable Development and we will ask an official endorsement by the Steering Committee.

3.3. Presentation of the scientific and technical leader and of the project team

Briefly present the scientific and technical leader of the project, the laboratory with which they are affiliated and the key lecturer-researcher(s) / researcher(s) / personnel involved. Any CVs should be included in the appendices.

Two researchers of NeuroMarseille are co-PI of this project.

Daniele Schön is DR CNRS and leader of the DCP team at INS, expert in **cognitive neurosciences** and in particular in neurosciences of music and language. In the last years he has questioned the changing scales in science and has joined different initiatives on sustainable science (eg. labo1.5, Atecopol Marseille). He is currently leading a project on the brain dynamics of cooperative and competitive verbal and musical behaviour (ANR Muscoord).

Julien Lefevre is MCF HDR in **computer science**, expert in modelling of brain morphogenesis at INT. He has led the young researcher ANR project "Modegy". He is involved in the interdisciplinary master on computational and mathematical biology, affiliated to Centuri Institute. For 3 years he has been in charge of the coordination of sustainable development at UFR Sciences, with Raquel Bertoldo (also partner of this project). He is also a member of the Ecoinfo Network focussing on the environmental impacts of AI and on how to teach sustainability questions in computer science.

Daniele Schön and Julien Lefevre are both already part of a large interdisciplinary Institute (ILCB Institute of Language Communication and the Brain), where Daniele Schön leads an interdisciplinary team on communication (phonetics, cognition, computational neuroscience, information theory).

Daniele Schön and Julien Lefevre, as well as other partners of the current project, are also on the initiative of a Neuro Green group within the NeuroMarseille Institute, that took form about one year ago and that gave birth to the current project.

Finally, while the technical leaders have a large experience in handling interdisciplinary projects with multiple partners at a national and international levels, this expertise becomes even more solid when considering the ensemble of the partners that have been or are directly involved in large scale projects targeting both research and education (PhD program in Neuroscience, CIVIS, Centuri, ILCB, Master in Cognitive Sciences, Master in Neuroscience).

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3.4. Presentation of the partner(s) involved

Briefly present the external organisation(s) involved in the project - if applicable - along with their role and the teams involved in the partnership. Provide the necessary elements to allow others to grasp what these partners contribute to the project, and their role(s) in the project.

One of the strength of this project is that **it encompasses the whole NeuroMarseille community**. This is clearly visible when considering that 9 Laboratories out of 9 are represented in the current project. Thus, to a certain degree, presenting all partners is presenting NeuroMarseille. Below we list the different individuals according to their expertise.

Cognitive science & neuroscience: Daniele Schön & Manuel Mercier (INS), Marie Montant & Thierry Ripoll (LPC), Christine Deruelle & Nicole Malfait (INT), Mireille Besson, Marieke Longcamp, Vincent Hok, Caroline Strube (LNC).

Fundamental Neurosciences: François Feron & François Devred (INP), Ivo Vanzetta (INT), Pascale Quilichini (INS), Pierre-Pascal Lenck Santini (INMED), Christophe Beclin, Francis Castets et Karine Narbonne-Reveau (IBDM), Païkan Marcaggi (UNIS).

Computer science: Julien Lefevre (INT), Arnaud Le Troter (CRMBM), Simon Moré (LNC)

Imaging and Engineering : Christian Bénar & Jean-Michel Badier (MEG Centre), Jean-Luc Anton (MRI Centre), Virginie Callot, Claire Costes, Olivier Girard, Wafaa Zaaoui & Joevin Sourdon (CRMBM), Thomas Chaigne (Fresnel).

Social Psychology : Raquel Bertoldo (Laboratoire de psychologie sociale, LPS)

Ethics : Caroline Strube (Mission intégrité scientifique au CNRS, LNC), Christine Deruelle (AMU ethics committee)

While all partners truly adhere to the interdisciplinary approach and will be active across all workpackages, we could generally state that the Cognitive science & neuroscience partners will greatly contribute to WP1, by proposing different research lines related to the actual crisis. The Fundamental Neurosciences partners, most of whom work in wet labs, will play a key role in redefining good Laboratory practices (WP3). The Computer Science and Imaging communities will play a role both in terms of research projects to estimate/optimize energy consumption as well as in terms of redefining good numerical practices (WP1&3). Finally all partners, but in particular those in Ethics, Social Psychology and Cognitive Science will play a major role in addressing WP2, studying the evolution of the importance played by environmental issues within the NeuroMarseille community.

4. Implementation modalities

4.1. Plan of action

Present activities in terms of objectives, tasks, deliverables, and criteria to measure success that can be used to evaluate the results at the end of the project. Add as many Work Packages as necessary. The schedule for the various tasks and their interdependencies may be presented in graphical form (e.g., Gantt diagram).

Insert as many WP as necessary

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Title of Work package 1 (WP1): Neurosciences for Green	
Start ³ : M1	End ³ : M36
Objectives: The aim of WP1 is to encourage scientific audacity in addressing the more and more compelling questions that we face due to the environmental crisis.	
<p>Description of the activity:</p> <p>In practice, we will propose 12 internships on the theme of neuroscience and ecology to L3, M1 and M2 students. The research questions will span the various disciplines represented by the different partners involved in the project. Topics may include, for instance [not exhaustive]: insights on social/human behaviour and specific representations involved in the climate crisis, study eco-anxiety/solastagia and related neuro-cognitive processes (e.g. denial, cognitive dissonance, cognitive biases, representation of scales and action consequence in time), assess and reduce the ecological footprint of neuroinformatics, discuss the new ethical questions originating from the ecological crisis.</p> <p>Understanding the dynamics of decision making in conflictual contexts. One of the major challenges in facing the climate crisis is to change our habits. In cognitive terms this means to decide to act for a change that is not immediately favourable for the actor. This recalls the cognitive dissonance theory wherein an attitude change is driven by a conflict and fosters reluctance for change [18]. In the specific case, the conflict is between the pleasure linked to our habits (e.g. taking a long shower) and the negative impact on the environment. Several internships will be proposed on these topics. For instance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questioning the notion of spatial and temporal scales that are particularly relevant for building/estimating cognitive representation and driving goal-directed action. Indeed, it is known that the longer the delay interval to obtain a reward, the smaller the subjective value of the reward. These phenomena seem to partly involve the limbic system weighting prediction [19, 20]. While these questions have often been addressed in reference to neuroeconomy, they are certainly of great importance to understand the difficulty in making choices with impact visible only in the long term. • We also have the capacity to address questions on the brain dynamics undergoing cooperative and competitive behaviour [21, 22]. during a dyadic verbal interaction. This is highly relevant to understand the factors that allow changing the balance in favour of cooperative behaviour. Similar questions can be addressed in the framework of altruistic behaviour (towards other individuals as well as towards nature, see [23]) These questions can be addressed in adults as well in children. A developmental approach will allow to sensitize children early on to environmental issues and possibly influence their behaviors toward respectful attitudes toward nature. It will be of great interest to follow the brain dynamics associated to such 	

³Example. M1, M6 etc. for month 1, month 6.

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changes in behaviour.

Another timely line of research overlapping with the field of neuroscience is the one related to eco-anxiety. Eco-anxiety refers to any form of anxiety which is related to the ecological crisis including climate change, deforestation, species extinction and pollution (e.g., [24]). Symptoms are now well described, they comprised both cognitive-emotional and functional impairment and could be associated, in the most serious cases, with depression, trauma and stress. Several recent survey papers established that nearly 60% of responders felt 'very worried' or 'extremely worried' about climate change, in particular the youngest [25]. However, although more and more people are concerned about this issue, there is a serious lack of studies on the mechanisms underlying eco-anxiety, its time course over life, how is it distinguishable from other type of anxiety, how is it related to specific cognitive or emotional profiles, how the effects of eco-anxiety can be reduced by emotional regulation strategies.

Within the framework of a master's or bachelor internship, it is possible to address many of these questions, either through literature reviews, or by using protocols and designs directly inspired from cognitive neuroscience. These internships will be made possible thanks to the strong association that some teams of the consortium have with psychiatrists (e.g. INT, INS).

- As an example, a subject of training course will be centered on the nature of the emotional states associated with eco-anxiety symptoms. A broad range of negative emotions have been associated to eco-anxiety but this has generated inconsistent interpretations in the literature. The use of fMRI may help to address this issue. Having a direct access to the brain activity induced by visual scenes displaying climatic disasters compared to other disasters, for example, will help elucidate whether specific type of emotion and brain networks underlie the eco-anxiety symptoms and envisage to orient future therapies.
- Another relevant question is whether negative emotions could be regulated to be less invasive, and what kind of emotion regulation strategy is the most efficient. In experimental studies of emotion regulation, the subject is asked to use a given strategy when exposed to an emotion-eliciting stimulus (here a degraded environmental context). More precisely, the aim is to compare the effect of different types of strategies (reappraisal, distancing, distraction and suppression) both on behaviour and brain dynamics (for a review, see [26]).

Reducing the ecological footprint of neuroinformatics: The environmental impact of computing and especially artificial intelligence (AI)/machine learning has gained more and more attention in the recent years. It is relevant for a neuroscientific community to address this question for two main reasons : 1) AI in its current connexionist version comes from pioneering works in neuroscience and is more and more intertwined with neurocomputational modelling, 2) neuroscience and in particular neuroimaging is a community with raising needs in machine learning methods. Two internships will be proposed :

- Achieve an exhaustive exploration of the projects in Neuromarseille labs using artificial intelligence by collecting information about 1) the software used with emphasis on deep learning architectures 2) the hardware facility, from individual GPU to collective solutions for

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instance local servers or AMU mesocenter. The goal of this internship is two fold: 1) to achieve a life cycle analysis of AI research practices [27] (ref) or at a minima having a quantification of global warming potential (GHG emissions). 2) to identify mutualization opportunities among the labs of Neuromarseille.

- This global approach will be combined with a more focused quantification and optimization of deep learning algorithms. Several tools allow to achieve these aims, from coarse online calculators, based on computation time and network architecture to more integrated tools quantifying precisely the number of floating point operations per seconds. We will use wattmeters, an original option that, to our knowledge, has not yet been addressed in the AI community.

These topics are not extensive and other aspects could be included such as: neuromorphic architectures for AI which are supposed to be more energy efficient; the ethical implication of AI. These internships will be coordinated throughout partners and proposed to students within a global **neuroscience for « green package »** consisting in a coherent ensemble of 12 internship proposals that will be distributed along the duration of the project. Partners will have regular meetings (1/month) that will allow a truly interdisciplinary education (see WP2). A collegiate procedure will allow to select each year the topics of the internships. Projects involving two supervisors from different Laboratory will be given priority (WP Coordinators: Deruelle, Montant, Schön). Timing : year 1, 2, 3

Resources involved (including human, material, technical, financial, contributions of partners, etc.)

The MRI Centre, the CRMBM and the MEG Centre (partners of the current project) have already agreed to allow pilot experiments free of charges and to give technical support to setup and analyse the selected projects. These Centres are specialised in cognitive paradigms and have all necessary equipment for complex cognitive and behavioural paradigms as well as advanced structural MRI imaging. This greatly reduces the financial cost of the project.

Moreover, other facilities will be available for free, such as EEG, TMS-EEG and eye-tracking-EEG, as these instruments are available in several Laboratories partners of the project.

The grant will cover 10 out of the 12 internships for the whole project duration on the different sub-topics described above (cognition, eco-anxiety, AI).

Expected results (deliverables, indicators): We expect that across the three years of the project, we will have more and more researchers that will propose internships on this topic (2 in year 1 up to 6 in year 3). We also expect that some of the selected internships will lead to publications and that some of the selected students will continue onto a PhD project (at least 2). Importantly, this project will promote research that will help to better understand the complex human behaviour facing the environmental challenges. Under an educational perspective, the dynamics raised on this topic will allow the emergence of specific educational units that will become part of the Master program (or the bachelor's degree). Finally, this project will boost interactions across the different NeuroMarseille Laboratories, and thus greatly favour interdisciplinarity.

Comments / Analysis: Because we strongly believe that broadening the education of the future generations of neuroscientists is of uttermost importance, we are also considering to open a discussion

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with other Neuroscience Master programs, in France and abroad. This will lead to a **national or international educational event** on the topics described above, towards the end of the project (6500 euros).

Title of Work package 2 (WP2): Towards new eco-responsible neuroscientific paradigms

Start³: M1

End³: M36

Objectives: The aim of the WP2 is to delineate scenarios for the neuroscience at the anthropocene era

Description of the activity:

While the aim of WP1 is to reorient neuroscientific questions toward concrete applications for the environmental crisis, WP2 aims at adopting a broader perspective for neurosciences, as a scientific field inscribed in an history, with human and non-human actors. In particular it seems relevant to consider the different possible futures for neurosciences, given the context of Anthropocene and given the psychological, ethical and sociological dimensions of our community. For instance, there is a strong debate inside the scientific community in general to determine whether only technology and science can save us from the environmental crisis. The existence of such a debate has become more visible and the implications are of utmost importance and will affect future scientific orientations. To shed light on such debates and help the community to find its own (collective) positions we propose an innovative approach based on two modalities whose global objectives are 1) to encourage an interdisciplinary integration 2) offer a moment of collective intelligence to outline the path of neuroscience at anthropocene.

First, we will hold regular seminars and workshops. We will host experts from different disciplines (philosophy, sociology, psychology, anthropology, arts etc.) that will bring their own perspective on neuroscience at the era of anthropocene or more largely on the relation between science, society and environment. These experts are already involved in collective dynamics with innovative practice e.g. Ateliers Sciences, environnement et société (Eric Tannier, Sophie Quinton, INRIA) ; Atecopol (Jean-Michel Hupé, Toulouse among many others); Atelier repenser l'humain, repenser le vivant (Marie Montant et Joëlle Zask, AMU) ; Master of science strategy and design for the anthropocene led by Alexandre Monnin, Clermont). We will also invite colleagues from the neuroscience community who are already involved in new practices, such as Christopher Summerfield (Oxford), Charlotte Rae (Sussex), Guillaume Dumas (Montréal).

Second, we will track the evolution of the importance played by environmental issues within the NeuroMarseille community. This part of the project will be carried on by a *post-doc* specialised in social psychology in collaboration with the 'Centre des Sciences Sociales pour les Sciences' (C3S) of the UFR Sciences (Bertoldo). The approach is both quantitative and qualitative. Through a dialogical perspective, it will be possible to favour the emergence of as well as to assess the interdisciplinary dimension of our project. Following Bertoldo et al. [28], we will organize a series of debates between

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researchers in neuroscience and track the social dynamics across different sessions. We have already identified a certain number of promising (but not exclusive) questions:

- What role should play artificial intelligence in our society? What is the role of neuroscience?
- Do brain/human-computer interface (BCI) represent a threat or an opportunity for environmental impacts as stated by promoters of metaverse?
- How can scientists address new questions that traditional funding agencies are not inclined to finance because too risky or not enough “trendy”? (e.g. impact of LED on the retina, impact of 5G on brain activity)

Overall WP2 will allow delineating scenarios for the neurosciences at the era of anthropocene. (WP Coordinators: Bertoldo, Lefevre, Schön). Timing: post-doc year 2

Resources involved (including human, material, technical, financial, contributions of partners, etc.)

A post-doc will be hired to conduct the research project with a dialogical approach. This will require to organize structured meetings with different groups of researchers on the questions described above and other questions that may emerge. The post-doc will also be in charge of the organization of the external seminars for one year as well as of the supervision of one master internship. He/she will have a strong background in social psychology.

We plan to organize about 4 seminars each year with external speakers (9000 euros for the venue of speakers, over the 3 years). Other seminars will host speakers of the AMU community including (but not exclusively) members of the Consortium.

Expected results (deliverables, indicators):

Across the three years of the project, the number of researchers and students that will join the seminars will increase considerably thanks to the action of the research Unit representatives as well as our links with the Master tracks. An important indicator of interdisciplinarity will also be appreciated in the diversity of participants to the groups of the dialogical approach.

The dialogical perspective will lead to one or more publications in the field of social psychology. The discussions and results of this WP will also lead to opinion articles in high impact neuroscience journals. We also plan to document the status and the evolution of environmental crisis perception in a well-delimited scientific community through mainstream media, such as popularization conferences, book chapters and possibly tribunes in newspapers, following the example given by labos1point5 or Atecopol.

Comments / Analysis:

Nowadays, it is very difficult to find the time for this type of approach, somehow questioning the scientific practice in relation to societal changes and requiring to take some distance from most common everyday research practice. We strongly believe that taking this time is of great relevance for the future of neuroscience. Such relevance of WP2 is not to be found in the neuroscientific findings, but rather in its potential to strengthen a community around a new vision of “socially embodied” science and hence to bring new scientific orientations. WP2 draws a framework where new questions,

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such as the role of AI or BCI in society, become thinkable and legitimate. Interestingly, recently, similar initiatives, such as ATECOPOL Toulouse (although further away from neuroscience), have found their place in the institutional ecosystem, clearly showing that there is a need to include these discussions at an Institutional level.

Title of Work package 3 (WP3): Toward sustainable practices shared in Neuromarseille

Start³:M1

End³:M36

Objectives: The aim of the WP3 is gathering the scattered sustainable development initiatives in Neuromarseille and improving scientific and environmental practices

Description of the activity

WP3 aims at gathering and expanding the numerous but scattered sustainable development initiatives/groups of the different Neuromarseille laboratories and to spread it across the community. We will adopt a comprehensive approach to mitigate the footprint of research activities, establishing a common framework to guide all existing and future efforts toward sustainable scientific practices.

We plan two steps of actions: 1) assessing the environmental impacts 2) proposing a global plan to reduce the global impacts

1) We will continue, extend and improve the assessment of research carbon footprint. The units of Neuromarseille have progressed in this direction, but with different rhythms and different methodologies. Depending on the campus, units have more or less difficulties to evaluate their energy consumption. Sharing information and practices will benefit all the units. We will pay a specific attention to the following aspects:

- Considering the contribution of technical equipment specific of neuroscience. In the carbon footprint of research, a substantial part will consist in assessing the footprint of large research equipment such as MRI scanner, MEG or optical microscopes.
- Considering the contribution of computing facilities. We will inspect carefully the perimeter and the attribution of the carbon footprints (AMU mesocentre or local clusters).
- Inventing the different approaches for waste management in laboratories that have very different experimental setups .

2) Once the different environmental impacts have been quantified it is important to propose a global plan to mitigate them and evaluate its influence. We will follow several orientations:

- Sharing the virtuous practices and, when relevant, implement them across labs. Such good practices will go from resource consumption to coding and data management.
- Emphasizing the importance of theoretical work, to ask more precise questions and optimize data interpretation and allow data “recycling”.
- Using the dialogical perspective (see WP2) to tackle possible concrete and difficult collective

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<p>decisions, e.g. regarding the reduction of flights.</p> <p>(WP Coordinators: Quilichini, LeTroter, Lefevre). Timing : year 1, 2, 3</p>
<p>Resources involved (including human, material, technical, financial, contributions of partners, etc.) In each laboratory there are people in charge of sustainable development who will share the good practices. Coordinators of the workpackage will be in charge of collecting, optimizing and redistributing good practices.</p>
<p>Expected results (deliverables, indicators): First, we will propose a git repository to the Neuromarseille community to share good practices and indicators for life cycle analysis (e.g. carbon footprint). By harmonizing the quantification of impacts in our community we expect optimizing the estimation of global GHG emissions and comply with the ISO standards, used for instance by labos1point5 initiative. Second, we will offer guidelines to a broader community of neuroscientists, through a publication such as the “ten simple rules for” in PLoS collection. Finally, we will coordinate actions and engage discussions to expand good practices in the internal rules of procedure of each Laboratory, including, for instance, travelling quota, purchasing policy and technical resource management.</p>
<p>Comments / Analysis: Although this work will be carried out in neuroscience oriented labs, the intrinsic interdisciplinary nature of these research activities will help make the majority of recommendations valid for most laboratories. This will considerably broaden the impact of this initiative.</p>

4.2. Steering and administrative management

Indicate which resources will be mobilised within the research unit's administrative team, after consultation of the management

<p>Experience of the research unit in project management (European, A*Midex, ANR, etc.):</p> <p>The INS has a large experience in managing large scale projects (HBP, H2020, FHU, ERC, ANR). The management for the current project will be rather straightforward (CDD contract, internship conventions and traveling). The INS recently recruited an experienced General Secretary, Audrey Moreau, that will be in charge of the financial management together with Noémie Piazzoli, financial manager.</p>

Administrative contact person (if applicable)

Surname	<u>Moreau</u>
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First name	Audrey
Role	General Secretary
Contact details (E-mail + Tel)	audrey.moreau@inserm.fr
Estimation of the level of experience in management of research projects:	<input type="checkbox"/> Beginner <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confirmed

Financial manager

Surname	<u>Moreau</u>
First name	<u>Audrey</u>
SIFAC accreditation level	<input type="checkbox"/> Polyvalent <input type="checkbox"/> SIFAC Web <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SIFAC Qualified
Role	General Secretary
Contact details (E-mail + Tel)	audrey.moreau@inserm.fr
Estimation of the level of experience in management of research projects:	<input type="checkbox"/> Beginner <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confirmed

4.3. Scientific and strategic management of the project and the partnership

Describe the modalities of coordination, the principles of organisation, and the resources allocated to ensure monitoring and implementation of the project.

In practice, this project has two co-PIs that will coordinate the three different actions. Moreover, every WP has several coordinators that will insure the good functioning of each WP. Importantly, every Laboratory has one representative that will allow to easily reach the whole community. Monthly meetings will favour a good exchange between partners. A gender balanced jury with representatives of all Laboratories will select each year the internships to be funded. Finally, we already have a dedicated frama discussion group (open slack), a dedicated space to store shared material (AMU cloud) and we plan change this into a blog to increase visibility (e.g. hypotheses.org).

4.4. Communication and dissemination

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Describe the communication and dissemination plan, in particular the actions aiming to improve visibility of the project at the relevant scales (schedule, communication supports, networking, etc.).

Since all 9 Neuroscience Laboratories are taking part to the project, it will be easy to communicate within the AMU Neuroscience community. Moreover, at the local scale (AMU), we will also benefit of the support of the NeuroMarseille Institute as well as the ILCB and Centuri Convergence Institutes to communicate our actions. Our communication with students will also be secured via tight connections with the Directory boards of the different Master and PhD programs affiliated to our Laboratories. We have already informed the Department of Sustainable Development of AMU and took contact with the ITEM (Institute for Mediterranean Environmental Transition) that will facilitate a large dissemination of the seminars and workshops that we will organise. Moreover, the speakers we planned to invite play all important roles in other national or international initiatives, which will increase our visibility and networking capacity. Finally, on a more standard basis, we will communicate our research results using the standard scientific supports favouring open science (journals, conferences and the web).

5. Expected impact and returns

Describe the perspectives for scientific, pedagogical and technical returns, and the potential in terms of novel interdisciplinary approaches; the perspectives for adoption of the project within the Institute and/or the site, returns for the site in terms of visibility, synergy and partnerships; leverage effect on new funding (national and European) for:

- *The scientific and technical leader*
- *The partner(s)*
- *The Aix-Marseille site*

This project brings together a diversity of disciplines and professional profiles, including psychology, neuroscience, informatics, human-machine interface, AI, medical imaging, signal and image processing and modelling. The aim is to create bridges between neuroscientific knowledge and social environmental debates at the level of AMU and beyond. This will be possible thanks to the implication of **more than twenty members of the 9 different Laboratories (plus one affiliated team)** of the NeuroMarseille Institute, as well as a collaboration with the **Department of Social Sciences**. The innovative character of the project resides in adopting an ecological attitude in Neuroscience. This requires:

- taking on the responsibility in shedding light on the current state of ecological upheavals
- offering imaginaries beyond the technological paradigm

The foreseen actions include knowledge circulation (education, communication, scientific events), public questioning (public awareness, science popularization), and most importantly developing new ways of conducting research in the field of neuroscience that include, but go well beyond, open science initiatives.

Gathering a large number of scientists and methodological platforms (psychophysics, EEG, MEG, MRI, optical imaging, neurophysiology) of the NeuroMarseille community on the theme of sustainable science will foster a structuring effort on a topic that is going to play a major role in science making in

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the years to come. The broader perspective of the project is to ignite a transformation of scientific practices and education within the neuroscience research community, respectful of both environmental and socio-economic challenges. This transformation may also interest other scientific communities, providing new opportunities for interdisciplinarity.

This project is an excellent example of interdisciplinarity : not only does it cross traditional boundaries between several academic disciplines, but it also likens different schools of thought in order to respond to the new needs and questions that are emerging as a consequence of the climate crisis. We anticipate these needs and questions to become more and more compelling in the years to come. As such, this project has great potential to further leverage other research programs, at national and European levels, both on understanding climate crisis-related human behaviour and on how science making itself is affected by the crisis.

6. Budget

6.1. Detailed presentation of the budget for the project

Include the Excel document as appendix 1. This document must be filled out with the help of the financial manager selected to monitor the project if this option is retained, or an administrative manager from the research unit. This person will help the applicant scientific and technical leader to link each expense to a broader category of costs.

6.2. Overall justification of the budget

*In addition to the table, provide any general comments to justify the projected use of the financial resources and the links between A*Midex funding and other sources of funds.*

The budget of this project is rather straight forward. 55k€ will be used to pay one year post-doc to carry on the research described at WP2. 39k€ will be used to pay the 12 internships we plan to offer along the three years (~4/year, WP1). This is partly funded by the local Units own funding (~6k€). The remaining budget will cover for travel and accommodation expenses of the invited speakers as well as the organization of the educational workshop. The local units will also contribute financially to the travel expenses of the speakers (~3,5k€).

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7. Appendices

Appendix 1 (required): Excel version of budget

Appendix 2 (required): Letter of commitment from the scientific and technical leader of the Aix-Marseille-affiliated institute

Appendix 3 (required): Letter of commitment from the director of the research unit

Appendix 4 (required): Letter of commitment from each partner